

HUMAN RIGHTS VIOLATION-SOUTH ASIAN COUNTRIES

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1. ABSTRACT

History has seen the extraordinary bondage. To look forward into the future, we should know about the past, which took us to the present. What a breath taking sight it will be, when everybody is treated right. Consider the possibility that I request you to envision a world; where no differences had ever been created on the stance of Man and Woman, Rich and Poor, Old and Young, White and Black, Tall and Short, Hindus and Muslims, Jews and Christians, Nepalese and Bhutanese, Tamils and Sinhallas, Albanian and Iranian, Africans and Americans or You and Me, where no boundary of countries had ever been separated just to fought for their own Rights. A Right is a claim that we are justified in making. But the irony lies in here, Humans are being rebellious against it's own race and vary existence, just to claim their power and position violating the sole essence of HUMAN RIGHTS.

2. BACKGROUND

Now, the soul searching question is- WHAT ARE HUMAN RIGHTS, HOW THEY WERE CREATED & BEING VIOLATED since human immemorial. According to United Nation, there are total 30 Rights, which are usually lump together to be called as Human Rights. But it was long time in coming:

From the beginning, there were no such rights, in the event that you were in with the strong group, you were protected and in the event that you weren't-you weren't. At that point an individual named Cyrus the Great¹, chose to change human history, subsequently after winning

¹ <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Cyrus-the-Great>

Babylon in 539 BC, he set free every one of the slaves and surprisingly said: individuals have the opportunity to practice their own religion, regardless of what swarm they have a place with. Antiquarians recorded his words on a tablet known as "CYRUS CYLINDER"², and in actually like that basic liberties were conceived. The idea spreaded very quickly- to Greece, to India, and eventually to the Rome. It was noticed that, people generally follow some laws even they weren't told to, they called this Natural Rights. But it kept getting trampled on, by those getting in power. At that point after thousand of year later, they at long last get a lord to concur that nobody can overrule the Privileges of individuals, not even a ruler, which brought forth MAGNA CARTA LAW³ of 1215 AD. Anyway it still took a lot of English agitator pronouncing Autonomy. At that point came FRENCH UNREST (1789- 1799), which holds the thought much more grounded and more extensive. Despite of the Rights given, In France , 1800s General Major Napoleon overthrown the French Democracy and called himself an emperor of the world , but countries of Europe joint forces defeated him and drew up an international agreement, brought granting many Rights across Europe, but only across Europe. Then came the period of colonization in almost all South Asian countries & Human Rights were again a hot topic, but it wasn't that eaisy, two World War erupted, Hitler exterminated half of the Jews population in four-five bloody death camps, over 19 million people died; never had Human Rights been so terrifying close to extinction & never had the world so desperate for the change. Then Unites Nation came into the picture (1945) and in 1948 UNIVERSAL DECLARATION OF HUMAN RIGHTS was establish and the French concept of Natural Right finally became Human Rights. These Rights majorly includes- Right to Life, Equality before Law, No Torture& inhuman treatment, No Slavery, Right to Trial, Innocent until proven Guilty, Freedom to Movement and Residence and list goes on referring many other Rights

² <http://cyruscylinder2013.com/2012/10/what-is-the-cyrus-cylinder>

³ <https://www.oxfordreference.com/search?q=Magna%20Carta>

3. SOUTH ASIAN CONTEXT

Presently, foundation has been set down, everything appears to be settled and iron up. However the reality anyway is hard hit. On the off chance that individuals reserve the Privilege to Food and Sanctuary, for what reason are 16,000 kids biting the dust of starvation consistently; If individuals have The right to speak freely of Discourse, why thousands are in jail expressing their genuine thoughts; If individuals reserve the Option to Training, why more than billion of grown-ups incapable to peruse; If Bondage has really been annulled, for what reason are 27 million individuals still in slave today, more as twice as numerous as in 1800s. This shows certain corners of the world are as yet wrecked with hindrance of contrasts. One such district is SOUTH ASIA, where world has affirmed the most antiquated human tight violation, an ethno-cultural region, consisting more than 20% of world's population , speaking more than 650 different type of languages. A region which square up the eight most treasured countries of the world namely- Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, Nepal, Pakistan, India, Sri Lanka and The Maldives. For these countries, share a colonial legacy which battered, burished and left the vary spirit of states wounded.

If we dig deep down the diaries of bygone days, each one of these has came through the long battle of civil wars, ethnic cleansing, religious persecution, terrorism, censorship, heinous torture, child abuse, man slaughter and many other brutal laws by government, corrupting the vary soul of Human Rights.

3.1 AFGHANISTAN

After the raise of Taliban in 1898⁴, the country has went through many miseries. The basic freedom condition in this conflict assaulted country is far from fulfillment. 9/11 fear mongers assault on USA was a land mark in the history of psychological oppression on the planet. The USA assaulted Afghanistan and tossed Taliban. America drove NATO powers in Afghanistan under Operation Enduring Freedom and is still fighting an apparently ceaseless conflict. The executing of many NATO⁵ forces and a huge number of regular people in this nation has additionally not driven to improvement in the circumstance. The quantity of causalities, both military and civilian is expanding significantly.

3.2 SRI LANKA

26 years of battling for a different Tamil country in Sri Lanka is ideally reaching a conclusion. Prabhakaran is dead currently which probably implies end of furnished battle of Tamils for a different home land. Mahindra Rajapaksha is in upbeat disposition and seen kissing the land after his return from Jordan. This might be end of battling of war however not the finish of Tamil issues. The guerrilla war may start following not many long periods of quiet if the situation isn't dealt with cautiously. The Tamil Tigers, the L.T.T.E.⁶ (Liberation Tigers of Tamil Elam) has been fighting with the Sri Lankan government and army one of the fiercest war of the world. The exact number of deaths in this longest war is not known. The recent government forces' offensive against the Tigers made the human conditions in this strife torn island from bad to worse. Hundreds of thousands of civilians had to flee from the war zones.

⁴ https://www.usip.org/sites/default/files/2021-02/afghanistan_study_group_final_report_a_pathway_for_peace_in_afghanistan.pdf

⁵ <https://www.nato.int/nato-welcome/>

⁶ <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2009/4/28/the-history-of-the-tamil-tigers>

3.3 INDIA AND PAKISTAN CONFLICTS

These two countries witnessed the greatest migration in human history, as millions of Muslims trekked to West and East Pakistan, which resulted in terrifying outbreak of sectarian violence- a mutual genocide as unexpected. Since then two nations has co- existed uneasily. Many wars has been fought for territorial integrity and Pakistan's state sponsored terrorism targeted the innocent civilians of the country and bought political instability, which lead Pakistan into Grey List of Financial Action Task Forces (FATF)⁷. However, India itself delt with many such laws which exploits the fundamental virtue of Human Rights. Such as: Unlawful Preventive Detention laws⁸, Armed Force (Special Power) Act⁹, 1958. India ranks 140 in the Press Freedom Index 2019.

3.4 NEPAL

The little early Nepal is going to witness another upheaval in not so distant future as the recently framed government under Pushapa Kamal Dahal Prachanda fell over reconciliation of PLA into Nepal Armed force issue. The Constitution has not yet been composed and endorsed by the Constituent Assembly. The CPA is running in through climate and the chance of Maoists beginning again a Jan Andolan, the guerrilla war fighting, can't be precluded. That period had witnessed massive slaughter and basic liberties infringement by both government and Maoists for gigantic scope thusly any crash of harmony measure may lead to emerge of comparative circumstances. This would awfully influence our security environment across borders. Another administration is set to take over in Nepal under Madhav Nepal without the help of Maoists; subsequently the fragile harmony in this Himalayan nation. In the event that it occurs, another time of threats and human rights violation would start. The social texture of Nepal is with the end goal that a significant number of its threads are spread into Indian culture, hence improvement of such situation would deface the harmony in Indian Region additionally, a circumstance India cannot stand to have at this point.

⁷ <https://www.dawn.com/news/1390408>

⁸ <https://www.mha.gov.in/sites/default/files/A1967-37.pdf>

⁹ <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/what-is-afspa-and-where-is-it-in-force/article23648102.ece>

3.5 BHUTAN

Bhutan, a land locked country, under the rule of Constitutional Monarchy, which has the highest Gross National Happiness Index. However, shares the saddest past. In late 80s and early 90s, state –sponsored crime increased targeting Nepali –Speakers in the form of arrests, imprisonment, rape, looting & plunder, torture, demolition and arson of homes. In 1985, Government bought it's famous Citizenship Act which resulted into illegal immigration overnight, lot many people fled to Nepal as Refugees. They also prohibited teaching Nepali language in South Bhutan, curbing Religious Freedom and imposing language and culture of the Ngalongs.¹⁰

3.6 BANGLADESH

East Pakistan, which is currently called as Bangladesh, shares close history with India and Pakistan and gone through the unforgiving clash of common and criminal conflicts to arrive at the platform of Autonomous state. However, Bangladesh's Awami league led government crackdown on free speech, arresting critics & censoring media. Arrest under Digital Security Act (DSA) increased rapidly. Administration and policies violated refugee Rights and authorities arbitrarily detained over 300 refugees on Bhasan Char Island.

3.7 THE MALDIVES

An island country, prevalently known as 'THE TROPICAL HEAVEN', the bunch of all most 1190 little islands, out of which just 185 are occupied. This is the smallest free country in Asia and was an English settlement until 1965. Due to political instability from last 2-3 decades, significant Human Right illness included-allegation of torture by government authorities, an emergency was declared in 2018 for all most 45 days, after 2 learned judges were arrested & put behind the bars, human trafficking, criminalization of same – sex sexual conduct, lack of legal framework, attack on Human Rights Defenders, etc attracted many allegation on country for violating Human Rights.

¹⁰ www.bhutaniowa.org

4. CONCLUSION

After surpassing all the historical evidences in each of these countries, the evil of Human Right Violation continues today. People are not aware that they have the Rights at first place.

Nationalism and strong religious loyalties have created a dangerous amalgamation. These nations practice some sort of so – called Democracy. A people group is majority rule just when the humblest and the most fragile individual can appreciate the most elevated common, financial and social rights that the greatest and most remarkable posses. Only HUMAN RIGHTS holds the weapon to create the world and fill it with life. However, after so many bones of contention, bloodshed and affrays, people have survived all sorts of challenges. All these background fights bought a new wave for regeneration and improving ties with each other. This can be disclosed with the foundation of South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC), 1985. For resolving all their long suits & marching towards the more incomparable future.

5. REFERANCES

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